

STUDY ON FABRICATION OF CARBON NANOCOMPOSITE SHEETS AND APPLICATION TO THE MICROWAVE ABSORBERS

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Keywords: Carbon nanotube, Carbon nanofiber, Resin film, Tape casting, Electric property, Microwave absorber

1 Introduction

Carbon nano materials have been investigated to enhance the electrical conductivity of the polymeric composites [1, 2]. Especially, there have been many studies to apply the carbon nanocomposite laminate into the radar absorbing material (RAM) or structure (RAS), in which the carbon nanocomposite laminate is made of E-glass fiber/epoxy prepreg containing various kinds of carbon nano materials [3-6].

The characteristics of RAM are determined by the electrical property of the carbon nanocomposite laminates [6]. Recently, Kim *et al.* [7] presented the Salisbury screen type radar absorbing composite structures for wind turbine blades. They also showed that the dielectric lossy sheet of thin carbon nanocomposite laminates instead of the 377 Ω /sq resistive sheet in the traditional Salisbury screen absorber can reduce the thickness of the absorber [8].

To develop a proper manufacturing process of the carbon nanocomposite laminates for the absorbers, it is very important to understand how the process has effect on the property of composites because the electric property of the composites can vary according to the dispersion or alignment of the carbon nano materials even though the kind and the filler content are the same [9-10].

During the manufacturing process of the prepreg, the increased viscosity of the mixture of the polymeric resin and carbon nano materials make it difficult to coat the mixture evenly onto the surface of the textile. In this study, the hot-melt method is used to make the prepreg of a mixture of carbon nanotube (CNT) and carbon nanofiber (CNF). The variance of the electrical property of the composites during the process from the epoxy resin film to the

laminate was investigated. Finally, the absorber composed of the dielectric lossy sheet of thin carbon nanocomposite laminates was developed at the frequency band of 8.2-12.4 GHz (X-band).

2 Theory

Complex permittivity is simply expressed by $\varepsilon = \varepsilon' - j\varepsilon''$, where ε' is dielectric constant and ε'' is lossy term that is related with the ac electric conductivity of the material written as $\varepsilon'' = \omega\varepsilon_0\sigma_{ac}$ where ω is angular speed for frequency f , ε_0 is a dielectric constant for vacuum (or air) and σ_{ac} is the electric conductivity of the composites.

Fig. 1 shows the schematic drawing of the RAS composed of the lossy sheet, dielectric spacer and perfect electric conductor (PEC).

Fig.1. Schematic drawing of the proposed RAS [7,8].

The thickness of the spacer depends on the thickness and EM property of the lossy sheet as well as EM property of the spacer. When Glass/epoxy laminate of $4.659 - j0.171$ was used as the spacer material, the optimal spacer thickness for zero-reflection can be achieved as shown in Fig. 2. In Fig. 2, the spacer thickness can be reduced by using the lossy sheet of high dielectric constant [8].

Fig.2. Cole-Cole plot for the complex permittivity of the dielectric lossy sheet achieved according to the spacer thickness [8].

2 Experiment

2.1 Fabrication of dielectric lossy sheet

The electrical conductive composite films were made with carbon nano materials in which carbon nanofiber (CNF) (PYROGRAH-III (PR-19-XT-LHT) of APPLIED SCIENCE Inc. USA) and carbon nanotube (CNT) (CM-95 of HANWHA NANOTECH Co. Ltd., Korea) are equally mixed. Carbon nano materials are dispersed in epoxy resin using 3-roll calendar [11]. The epoxy resin is a Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin mixture.

The Doctor Blade Method was used to make resin film. The casting knife height was adjusted to get the 70- μ m thick resin film [12]. Fig. 1 shows cross sectional view of the casted resin film of 2wt.% of CNT and 2 wt.% of CNF. The carbon nano materials are well dispersed in the matrix. It must be noted that the casting method can make alignment of the fibrous fillers due to the directional operation [13]. In the comparison between the (a) casting direction and (b) transverse direction, it can be observed that CNFs are especially aligned along the casting direction.

The resin film was impregnated into an E-glass fabric at 80°C under vacuum bag under the condition that the warp direction of the fabric is parallel to the casting direction of the resin film. The E-glass fabric is #110 EPC glass mat supplied by HANKUK Fiber Co. Korea. The fabric mat is the plain weave type of which the fiber counts are 60 and 57 yarns/in. in

warp and fill direction, respectively, and the fiber aerial weight is 107 g/m².

To investigate the influence of the lamination sequence on the electrical property, laminates of [0], [0]2 and [0/90] were stacked and cured into an E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminate during 20 min at 80°C following 2 hours at 120°C under vacuum bag. Fig 2 shows the fractured section of the [0/90] laminate. The carbon nano materials are well distributed in the resin rich area of the laminate. The thickness of the laminate of 2 plies is 0.23 mm.

Fig.3. Cross sectional view of casted film in (a) casting and (b) transverse directions. CNT (2wt.%) and CNF (2wt.%) are aligned in casting direction.

Fig.4. SEM image of the fractured section of the [0/90] laminate [7].

2.2 Fabrication of RAS

RAS in this study is composed of a carbon nanocomposite sheet as the dielectric lossy sheet, a pure E-glass/epoxy laminate as the dielectric spacer and a carbon fabric/epoxy laminate as the PEC. The spacer is the 4 plies of E-glass $[\pm 45]$ bi-axial NCF (Non Crimp Fabrics of SAERTEX GmbH & Co. of German, SE1500 Glass fiber of Owens Corning of China) and one ply of #110 glass fabric used for the required spacer thickness. The thickness of the spacer is 2.2 mm. The PEC is carbon fabric (WSN3K of SK Chemicals of Korea, TR30 Carbon fiber of Mitsubishi Rayon of USA) of which nominal thickness is 0.227 mm. RAS was fabricated using SCRIMP process. The epoxy resin is EPIKOTE Resin MGS® RIM 135 and EPIKURE Curing Agent MGS® RIM H 137 (HEXION Specialty Chemicals, GmbH & Inc. of German). The epoxy resin was cured in room temperature.

2.3 Measurement of EM property

In order to measure the complex permittivity of composites and reflection loss of absorbers in X-band, Agilent N5230A and HVS free space measurement system was used as shown in Fig. 5 [14].

Fig.5. Free space measurement system for the measurement of complex permittivity and reflection loss.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 EM property of lossy sheet

The EM property of the resin film and laminates are measured under conditions that the casting direction is parallel and vertical to electric field of the transverse electromagnetic (TEM) wave transmitted from the measurement system. It is

obvious that the complex permittivity in casting direction is much higher than that in transverse direction. This difference results from the alignment of the carbon nano materials in the resin film.

To reduce the orthogonality of the electric property, carbon nanocomposite prepregs were fabricated by coating the #110 glass fabric with the tape-casted epoxy resin film. The variation of the EM property during the composite manufacturing process was investigated by observing the complex permittivity of $[0]$, $[0]_2$ and $[0/90]$ laminates. Fig. 6 shows the measurement results of the complex permittivity of resin films and composite laminates. Dir-1 means the casting direction of the resin film or x-axis of the laminate coordinate system and dir-2 means their transverse direction.

Fig.6. Complex permittivity of epoxy resin film and its carbon nanocomposite laminates measured in dir-1 (the casting direction of the resin film or x-axis of the laminate) and dir-2 (transverse direction)

As shown in Fig. 6, $[0/90]$ laminate shows the minimum orthogonality of the electric property. However, in the $[0/90]$ laminate, the high real part of the epoxy resin film in the casting direction disappeared to lose the opportunity of reduction of spacer thickness which is represented in Fig. 2.

3.2 RAS of nanocomposite sheets

RAS in this study needs the isotropic EM property and [0/90] laminates are applied for the dielectric lossy sheets. To design RAS, carbon nanocomposite laminates containing the mixture of 3.00 wt.% CNT and 3.00 wt.% CNF was fabricated and its complex permittivity were measured. Fig. 7 shows the complex permittivity of the sheet and the spacer and Fig. 8 shows the image of fabricated RAS.

Fig.7. Complex permittivity of the dielectric lossy sheet and the bi-axial E-glass NCF/epoxy laminate

Fig.8. Configuration of the fabricated RAS

Fig. 9 shows the reflection loss of designed and fabricated RAS. The -10 dB bandwidth of the measurement is over 3.74 GHz and the total thickness of the RAS is about 2.4 mm

4 Conclusion

The epoxy resin film containing the mixture of CNT and CNF and carbon nanocomposite laminates were fabricated. The resin film has very high dielectric constant in the casting direction but also has so high orthogonality of the EM property. The [0/90] composite laminate made of the resin film has nearly isotropic electrical property in its in-plane

direction but the dielectric constant of the laminate is much less than that of the resin film to lose the opportunity of reduction of spacer thickness when applied as the dielectric lossy sheet for RAS.

A Salisbury screen type radar absorbing structure in X-band was fabricated. The RAS is composed of a thin carbon nanocomposite laminate as the lossy sheet and a ply of carbon fabrics as the PEC, and the core of E-glass [± 45] bi-axial NCF (Non Crimp Fabrics). Even though the thickness of the developed RAS is about 2.4 mm, the -10 dB bandwidth is over 3.74 GHz.

Fig.9. Comparison between calculated and experimental reflection losses

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by New & Renewable Energy R&D Program (2008-N-WD08-P-02) under the Korea Ministry of Knowledge Economy (MKE).

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